

1 **CDK4 is activated in human lung cancer.**

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6 We report here the identification of CDK4 as a viable therapeutic target in human lung cancer. CDK4
7 was retrieved as an up-regulated and differentially expressed kinase using whole transcriptome technology that
8 measures and compares total transcription in normal lung tissue and human lung cancers (the primary tumor).
9 Overall survival (the amount of time from diagnosis until death) was over 2 years greater (26 months) in
10 humans with lung cancer whose tumors expressed low levels of CDK4 as compared to patients whose tumors
11 expressed high levels of CDK4; this was statistically significant. We have recently utilized multiple whole
12 transcriptome technologies to predict and demonstrate a likely and strong therapeutic benefit in humans with
13 hormone receptor positive (HR+) breast cancer, in humans with CNS metastatic breast cancer, in humans with
14 gastric cancer, and in humans with glioblastoma. These data indicate that the millions of patients with lung
15 cancer worldwide are also likely to benefit from adjunctive pharmacologic CDK4/6 inhibition from the -ciclib
16 family (palbociclib, ribociclib and abemaciclib).

Figure 1: CDK4 is differentially expressed and up-regulated in human lung cancer.

Probe ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
ILMN_1689001	2.70E-06	-5.430107	4.354517	-1.75973589	CDK4	3857/47229	91.8

Figure 2: Low CDK4 tumor expression is significantly correlated with superior overall survival in lung cancer.

Low tumor expression of CDK4: 80 months

High tumor expression of CDK4: 54 months